

Social media marketing: A new platform that influences Nigerian Generation Y to engage in the actual purchase of fast-moving consumer goods

Enitan Olumide Olutade

North-West University, South Africa, olumightyolutade@gmail.com

*Corresponding author

Abstract: The emergence of social media in marketing has transformed the business world and introduced new tasks to manage. Advertisers must live up to these ever-changing consumer desires and preferences. Social media marketing presented ample prospects to explore new groups of consumers underserved, popularly known as Generation Y. The social media marketing platform supports firms in creating a cordial relationship by personalising information for individual Generation Y consumers and influencing these groups of consumers to engage in the actual purchase. The purpose of this study was to establish social media marketing as a new platform that can influence Generation Y to engage in the actual purchase of fast-moving consumers in the Nigerian sample population. This study adopted quantitative research. This study captured 463 Generation Y. The completed data collection scale was through self-administered questionnaires (printed) and used online surveys. The population of this study consists of undergraduates full-time students of the University of Lagos, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional time horizon. In addition, the study adopted purposive and virtual snowball sampling. Inferential statistics results showed that the platform's convenience could easily influence purchases on social media marketing platforms, engagement on brand Fan-page events, and prior information about a brand. This study recommended that organisations targeting Generation Y be proactive on social media marketing platforms and partner their brand with trending influencers on social media platforms.

Keywords: Facebook, Fast-moving consumer's goods, Generation Y, Social media marketing, Social media platforms, WhatsApp

1. Introduction and background of the study

The emergence of social media marketing in marketing has transformed the business world and brought challenges to be tackled. At the same time, an advertiser must live up to these ever-changing consumer desires and preferences. This introduced ample prospects to explore new groups of consumers underserved, despite veiled opportunities abound within. Marketing stimuli are the new tools commonly used to trigger

Research Article: This article is published by *JFP Publishers* in the *Journal of Emerging Technologies (JET)*. This article is distributed under a Creative Common Attribution (CC BY-SA 4.0) International License. **Conflict of Interest:** The author/s declared no conflict of interest.

Generation Y's needs and want to influence their actual purchase. Today, many fast-moving consumer goods (FMCGs) firms have started to adopt digital platforms as a strategy but have miles to go in social media marketing (McKinsey & Company, 2019). A report on gross expenditure on household (FMCGs) in Africa showed that World Bank's Global Consumption Database revealed that FMCGs expenditure was highest in Nigeria (US\$41.7bn). However, social media is influencing how young consumers and advertiser communicates. Maw (2016) confirmed that social media enhanced the business interaction between organisations and Generation Y consumers, and this would surely yield progressive sales volume for firms marketing FMCGs.

At present, social media is recognised as a vital part of integrated marketing communication (IMC), and it is an influential tool that can impact young consumer attitudes favorably or unfavorably organisation towards a brand (Naumovska, 2017). However, it is unfortunate that a significant integer of FMCGs organizations in Nigeria is yet to engage with Generation Y on this economic platform. Past and present studies (Stephen 2016; Stueber & Wurth 2017; Arrigo, 2018; Busalim, Hussin, & Iahad, (2019) are predominantly desktop analyses with findings not based on empirical studies, such as the study of Stueber and Wurth (2017). These scholars reviewed thirty scientific articles obtained from various databases. Similarly, Stephen (2016) findings were based on secondary data from reviewing recently published research works related to social media marketing. This study, however, is exclusive and original due to it is empirical. This study aimed to establish social media marketing as a new platform that influences Nigerian Generation Y to purchase fast-moving consumers in the Nigerian sample population.

Following this introduction, the literature review was presented as related to formulated research objectives of this study. The paper then briefly examines the adopted theoretical framework that underpinned the study. The study further showcased the research hypothesis tested. Next, the study succeeded in the presentation of research methodology, research results, and discussion. This paper terminates with a conclusion and recommendation.

1.1. Purpose and objectives of the study.

For this study, quantitative research methodology and ordinal logistic regression (OLR) analysis was adopted to present social media marketing as a new platform that can influence Generation Y to engage in the actual purchase of fast-moving consumer goods in Nigeria. The rationale is to establish and estimate the relationship between variables. Therefore, the study's objective is to selected social media marketing platforms as a significant factor that triggers younger generations to engage in the actual purchase of fast-moving consumer goods.

2. Literature review

This section of the study provides vital associated literature with that spotlight brings spotlight the overview and relevance of social media marketing. This segment expounds on Generation Y attitude and their associated popular social network in Nigeria.

2.1. Overview of social media marketing

Furthermore, the Nigerian Internet market is brand as the biggest in Africa with over 125 million mobile telephone subscribers; 35 million people access the Internet through their respective mobile phones (Olotewo, 2016). The researcher further stresses that Nigeria still maintains the leading Internet market within Africa continent due to its vast fraction of young people (one-third of the population falls in the range of 10-24 years age bracket). The Internet's geometric progression welcomed the popular notion of digital marketing and social media marketing (Bekoglu & Onayli, 2016), starting with digital marketing. Artemova (2018) aver that

indisputably, social media marketing (SMM) is just a segment of the more significant digital marketing section. Furthermore, Mkwizu (2019) acknowledges that social media marketing is a vital technique in digital marketing.

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) were the foremost scholars that broadly defined social media. Both authors described social media as a collection of Internet-based applications that hinges on the philosophical and high-tech of Web 2.0 that permit the development and exploits the usage of online individual produced content. Olutade and Chukwere (2020) describe social media as a Web 2.0 platform that enables reliable information sharing to inform pictures, texts, pictures and audio among the characterised online group that offers unlimited opportunities for an organisation. A previous study by Olabanji, Shumba and Tafadzwa, (2014) terms social media marketing as a platform that empowers organisations to engage in a communal discourse with their target consumers to generate a win-win post-sales experience. Artemova (2018) defines social media marketing as a process of exploring information technology to build, link, and offer value to the target consumers. Olotewo (2016) views social media marketing as a technique of selling firms offerings via social media platforms. Thus, it is the incorporation of social media platforms into marketing activities.

2.2. Relevance of social media marketing

Social interaction application offered via social media platform helps increase trust and minimises perceived risk (Hajli, 2014). Generation Y's interconnectivity through social media, such as opinions, as a prospect to establish trust in social media marketing. Brands' social presence aids integrity in relevant communities (Wang, Yu, & Wei 2012). The social media marketing platform supports the firm in creating a cordial relationship by personalising information for individual Generation Y consumers and allowing target consumers to become co-producers of their wants and preference brand.

The use of blogs, microblogs, and social networking sites can accelerate the traffic towards organisation websites and brand pages. The social media platform aid brand page search engine optimisation (Ciprian, 2015). FMCGs brand can reach enormous users more impulsively with low budget planning via social media. Icha and Edwin (2016) report that the majority of FMCGs firms acknowledged social media platforms as crucial tools for brand exposure. Remarkably, in emergent markets such as Nigeria, social media marketing is rapidly growing, but the shortage of social media marketing professionals reduces the platform's benefits. More so, inadequate skills hinder many social media practitioners from leveraging attributes available on the platform to loyal customers, informing of followers, likes, and tweets; this is one of the significant challenges affecting SMM adoption in emerging markets such as Nigeria (Olotewo, 2016). Lastly, social media marketing empowered Generation Y with information that aids them in making rational buying decisions. The subsequent section delves into Generation Y

2.3. Generation Y

Generation Y was born in the ideal age of information technology. These Generation Y treasure and adore technology as a routine activity to live stress-free and more ingenious. This generation is digital natives, a cohort that loves excitement and showbiz memoirs. Advertisers understand that investing in social media marketing is the ultimate approach to influence this young cohort due to the revelation of the available record that over 55% of Generation Y are enthusiastically open on this social media network (Shivakumar, 2018). There are four kinds of cohorts recognised among scholars, viz. the Silent generation (Silent), Baby Boomers (Boomers), Generation X (X-ers) and Generation Y (Bevan-Dye, 2016; Futurum Research, 2016). This Generation Y are often called Millennials and Native digitals. They are the remarkable generation of youth in the society who possesses associated attributes in terms of behaviour and attitude towards promotion stimuli (Krbová, 2016).

Specifically, for this study, Generation Y is the population born between 1985 and 2020, representing this age group between 18 and 35 years old in the year 2020 (data collection period). For the significance of statistical consistency among Nigeria Generation Y, the classification confirmed by the African Union (2006), “every person between the ages 18 and 35 years”, was adopted in this study. Furthermore, Bevan-Dye (2016) avers that Generation Y grew up having more accessibility to global related information such as brand, price comparison, after-sales services, online product demonstration videos and competing brands. Generation Y is comfortable and cheerful with the development in information communication and technology, technologically intelligent, savvy in mobile phones to get access to social media, which has become a regular and vital part of their daily routine (Zhang, Omran & Cobanoglu, 2017). Having briefly discussed Generation Y, the subsequent section will address Generation Y popular social network in Nigeria.

2.4. Generation Y popular social network in Nigeria

For this study, the social networking sites of Facebook and WhatsApp were selected based on their popularity and relevance to this study.

2.4.1. Facebook

The Facebook website was created and launched on February 4, 2004, by Mark Zuckerberg alongside his colleagues and friends for Harvard University student’s usage in the United States (Mbanaso, Dandaura, Ezeh, & Iwuchukwu; Pasma, 2017). Facebook is a free platform of social networking sites that permits individuals around the globe to registered and voluntarily create user’s profiles, post pictures, and videos, keep in touch with loved ones. Su and Chan (2017) reported a variety of applications and features that enhance relationship building provided by Facebook, such as liking, sharing, commenting, and messaging options. Facebook allows Generation Y of the similar opinion, who are in the same discipline to connect over the Internet to learn and disseminate meaningful information (Thurairaj, Hoon, Roy & Fong (2015)

Osazee-Odia (2017) reported that more than 7.2 million Nigerian use Facebook daily; 97% of them use a mobile phone to reach their respective social network. Facebook is well known among Nigerian Generation Y, as most advertisements in the FMCGs industry target these young cohorts (Akpan, Nwankpa & Agu, 2015). Rehman, Ilyas, Nawaz, and Hyder (2014) affirm that Facebook has become a marketing network for advertisers to reach their respective target consumers with low budgets. Facebook offers its platform as a marketing place via its Facebook marketing, which provides owned media, Facebook ads, and earns media (Pasma, 2017). In a nutshell, Africa Practice (2014) emphasises that Facebook is losing active users to other social media platforms in Nigeria and other African nations.

2.4.2. WhatsApp

WhatsApp was initiated and founded by Brian Acton and Jan Koum, former employees of Yahoo. It is a better alternative to a short message service (SMS) that connects to smartphones. Facebook later acquired the WhatsApp platform for 19 billion US Dollars on February 19 2014 Akintola, Bello, and Daramola, (2017), Alsanie (2015) and Mefolere (2016) provide evidence that WhatsApp messenger is well known across the social media mobile messaging application as an instant messaging subscription service for mobile phones, which offers selected phone features and attributes connected to the Internet to enhance interaction. WhatsApp is a social network that enables people from different backgrounds to access vast information rapidly. According to Statista (2017), figures showed lively 1.2 billion people who access WhatsApp monthly. This platform is easy to use, affordable, fast, and prompt. In Nigeria, this mobile instant message application (WhatsApp) has over 5 million users (Akintola *et al.*, 2017). Sanusi, Gambo and Bashir (2014) claim that WhatsApp is a social media that is a widely used platform among Generation Y in Nigeria for academic purposes.

Lastly, Akintola *et al.* (2016) researched Nigeria among 387 undergraduate students who identified WhatsApp as their favourite social media platform. The Africa Practice (2014) discovered that WhatsApp is

one of the mobile chat applications with the most users in Nigeria. The subsequent section delves into the theoretical framework underpinning the study.

3. Theoretical framework

3.1. Technology Acceptance Framework (TAM)

The technology acceptance model (TAM) essentially replaces the philosophy of reasoned action (TRA). TAM reveals that the actual use of information technologies anchored upon a consumer's attitude towards that information platform, such as the perceived ease of use and the perceived benefits would be obtained exploring it. (Salwani, Marthandan, Norzaidi, and Chong 2009; Mulero, 2012). Behaviour as a concept was projected using the dual variables of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977). It is deduced from this TAM model (see Figure 1) that if Generation Y perceives that particular skill will support them in achieving specific goals, then young cohorts will gladly embrace it. Whenever Generation Y experience high system quality or information quality, they will most probably be more likely to partake in the actual buying situation. The empirical studies of Mulero (2012) and Hajli (2014) indicate that perceived usefulness has more influence than trust on intention to buy. Mulero (2012) maintains that when a new skill is been observed as being stress-free to use, then consumers rapidly embrace its usage. The perceived use of ease technology and the perceived benefits can be resulting from using it. This is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Source: Adapted from Davis (1989)

Perceived usefulness plays a vital role in social media marketing platforms (Hajli, 2014). The research results on the actual purchase via social media marketing platforms revealed that the Generation Y shop on social networking platforms they perceive as valuable, the more actual investments they will engage in via these platforms (Jiyoung, 2009). Thus, FMCGs organisations need to realise and promote the benefits of using social media platforms and incorporate them effectively and resourcefully into their marketing activities. Then actual sales behaviour will surely come alive.

Research Hypothesis: Social media marketing platforms do influence Generation Y to engage in the actual purchase.

Generally, information gathered from the actual purchase can help identify the marketing strategy, consumer wants and preferences, and ensure the business stability. A Previous study discovered that actual purchase is complex and differs by segment (Victor, Thoppan, Nathan & Maria, 2018). A survey conducted by Ismail and Mokhtar (2016) addresses basic purchase behaviours as a consumer's willingness and disposition to participate in buying a specific brand/product. The rapid penetration of social media marketing, especially in developing countries such as Nigeria, offers marketers a new platform to increase future relationships with

Generation Y within and outside the country (Duffett, 2017). FMCGs organisations are working strategically to improve the time these young cohorts spend with their brands on social media marketing platforms. Social media marketing is predominantly peer-influenced regarding actual purchase decisions among Generation Y (Gupta, 2016).

Furthermore, Thaichon (2017) asserted that virtual friends could be considered a source of influence and considerably affect the consumer specialisation process. A previous study by Josh and Vaghela (2015) declared that the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness impact person behaviour toward the usage of information communication technology (ICT). A study conducted by Davis (1989) identified the predictor of actual behaviour to be information technology, for example, the technology acceptance model (TAM). The researcher recognised perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness as a factor influencing a person attitudes in using an information system. Given Currás-Pérez *et al.* (2013) prove that social media platforms allow users to access their bosom friends, loved ones and contemporaries, and strangers. Social networking sites, such as WhatsApp, permit organisations to build the brand forum, and people that follow the brand forum will get and share the latest brand related information (Coulter & Roggeveen, 2012).

Various payment applications emerged as advancements in technology, such as blockchain and. Hence, this inspires online payment and crypto currency societies among Generation Y in Nigeria. Contrary to the above, Elms, De Kervenoael, and Hallsworth (2016) comment that the information technology driven age offers quite different knowledge of shopping that completely differs from bricks and mortar. Kowalska (2012) affirmed another motive for online purchases, which was traceable to convenience, time-saving, and different brands compared to an affordable price. KPMG (2017) argues that as part of the emerging marketing concept to satisfy consumers. Generation Y cherishes online payment and after-sales services, door-step delivery services, bulk purchases discount, credit facilities, and genuine guarantees or warranty services exceed their expectations. Lautiainen (2015) posits that the reason behind consumer loyalty to a specific brand is deeply locked in their minds. Generation Y tries to satisfy their wants and preferences by purchasing for themselves or satisfy the need of others by buying for them (Lautiainen, 2015).

In addition, Duffett (2017) establishes that actual purchase behaviour is deliberate, intentional, and pre-mediated behaviour demonstrated by an individual towards possession of a particular brand or product. The rapid penetration of social media marketing, especially in developing countries such as Nigeria, offers marketers a new platform to have boosted future relationships with Generation Y (Duffett, 2017). Today, social media reviews and recommendations have started affecting Generation Y's purchase decision process (Gupta, 2016). This aids satisfied Generation Y to recommend a brand to other potential users. FMCGs organisations are working strategically to increase the time these young cohorts spend with their brands on their respective social media marketing platform. Social media serves as a significant peer influencer when targeting Generation Y to engage in actual purchases (Gupta, 2016).

As more information and communication technology (ICT) improvements such as blockchain and various transaction applications emerge, the trend to shift to cashless and cryptocurrencies societies among Generation Y is evolving. Ismail and Mokhtar (2016) propose that brands create a platform that possesses attributes of stress-free online payment that boost the relationship and improve quality services to these young cohorts. Similarly, Hajli (2014) affirms that perceived usefulness has more influence over trust as an intent to purchase via social media platforms. Still, the study of Ismail and Mokhtar (2016) state that intends to buy a particular brand is an integral part of predicting actual purchase. Based on the above discussion and in-depth correspondence with the social media marketing postulated by the factors influencing Generation Y purchase, it is posited that H1: Social media marketing platform affects Generation Y to engage in the actual purchase. The following section presents the research methodology adopted for this study to achieve the stated objectives of this study.

4. Methodology

The section of this study provides a summary of the methodology applied in this study. Quantitative research was adopted in the course of this research. Creswell (2014) avow that quantitative research enhances the testing of theories by examining the existing relationships among interacting variables. The study analysis was measured using complex statistical instruments while data is analysed using statistical procedures. The population of this study consists of all the undergraduates' students in the university of Lagos. This total study population stood at 23 653 full-time undergraduate students in University Lagos Akoka, Nigeria. The sample size of these Generation Y was derived using the sample size calculator of Research Advisor (2006) by ensuring a 95% confidence interval and 0.035 margins of error. The calculated sample size was 536 from the University of Lagos.

The pilot study conducted was with 30 respondents from the University of Lagos. Remarkably, two experts were requested that provided insight into the contents of the questionnaire items. The full scale of data collection was through self-administered questionnaires (printed) and online format (Google forms). The survey data drawn was from young consumers (undergraduates) from Nigeria between 18 and 35. Data were analysed using a statistical package for social science (SPSS). A sample questionnaire was uploaded on the online survey through the Google form to generate a link to the study. The survey link generated was posted on various social media platforms and instant messaging tools such as Facebook and WhatsApp. The study adopted a cross-sectional time horizon because respondents completed the survey at a single point in time. The main reasons for collecting data from this Generation Y are tech-savvy, technologically open, and mindful of their uniqueness, and open to FMCGs brands. Purposive and virtual snowball sampling was adopted in the study. The subsequent exposition delves into results analysis. The first was the demographic information presented, followed by the research results.

5. Result and discussion

5.1. Demographic information

The study captured 463 respondents. This high response rate was due to the questionnaire posted online (using Google forms) and pen-on-paper questionnaires (print) provided to accessible respondents for whom it was convenient to participate. In the biographical information, 58% were males, and 42% were females. In their marital status, married 32(8%) while singles 426 (92%) In their current study of level, 20% were in 1st year, 34.% were 2nd year, 27% were 3rd year, and 16% were in 4th year and 3% in the 5th year. Regarding their age, 18-20years 152(33%), 21-23years 128(28%), 24-26 years 69(15%); 27-29years 36(8); 30-32years 33(7) and 33-35years 45(9).

5.2. Descriptive analysis

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of actual purchase

N	ITEMS	Nigeria			
		SD%	D%	A%	SA%
	Statements				
F1	There is the possibility that in the future, my purchases of groceries and toiletries will be higher on social networking platforms.	8.4	20.7	46.4	24.4
F2	I will buy via social media if the organisation possesses good consumer service and high integrity.	3.0	8.4	53.1	35.4
F3	I will shop on social networking platforms if I have knowledge or information about a brand.	2.2	9.1	55.1	33.7
F4	My engagement on brand Fan-page events will influence me to purchase via social media.	5.2	14.5	55.7	24.6
F5	I will continue to purchase on social media as long as there are incentives for buying and participation.	4.3	13.8	53.6	28.3

F6	Buying on social networking sites gives me convenience and hasten my buying process.	3.7	15.1	49.5	31.7
----	--	-----	------	------	------

Table 1 indeed indicated results selected statements for Nigeria is F3. That is, for both combined highest positive and negatives regions in this study. For the highest combined positives, responses in F3(84.3%) indicated respondents agreed that they would shop on social networking platforms if they. In the same manner, is F3(88.8) displaying the highest combined positives indications. Notably, few respondents recorded relating to the lowest combined negative indication for Nigeria F3 (11.3). Respondents believe that buying on social networking sites does not give convenience and hasten any buying process. However, the response results show that most of Generation Y affirm favourably to those factors that influence Generation Y to engage in actual purchase on social media platforms. Overall, purchased on a social media marketing platform can easily be affected by the convenience of the platform, engagement on brand Fan-page events, incentives and knowledge or information about a brand.

5.3. Inferential Results: Ordinal Logistic Regression (OLR)

Table 2: OLR analysis of actual purchase

Construct - Section C	Actual Purchase (AP)											
Response Variables Items - Statements (S1- S6)	AP RSA1/ NIG1 There is the possibility that in future, my purchases of groceries and toiletries will be higher on social networking platform.		AP RSA2/ NIG2 I will buy via social media if the organisations possess good customer service and high Integrity.		AP RSA3/ NIG3 I will shop on social networking platform if I have knowledge or information about a brand.		AP RSA4/ NIG4 My engagement on brand fan page events will influence me to purchase via social media.		AP RSA5/ NIG5 I will continue to purchase on social media as long as there are incentives for buying and participation.		AP RSA6/ NIG6 Buying on social media marketing platforms gives me convenience and hastens my buying process.	
Predictor variable: Does social networking triggers you to engage in actual purchase of brand/product?												
	AP 01		AP 02		AP 03		AP 04		AP 05		AP 06	
	RSA	NIG	RSA	NIG	RSA	NIG	RSA	NIG	RSA	NIG	RSA	NIG
Model Fitting Information	0.006	0.004	0.001	0.016	0.024	0.133**	0.00	0.068**	0.08	0.209**	0.011	0.070**
Goodness of Fit (Deviance)	0.686	0.824	0.110	0.907	0.116	0.348	0.202	0.130	0.448	0.992	0.697	0.882
In(Odds)	0.588	0.672	0.739	0.586	0.506	0.373	0.788	0.450	0.613	0.300	0.587	0.426
Odds (Likelihood) Value	1.800	1.958	2.094	1.797	1.659	1.452	2.199	1.568	1.846	1.350	1.799	1.531
Test of Proportional Odds (Sig. Value)	0.686	0.824	0.110	0.907	0.118	0.348	0.202	0.130	0.448	0.992	0.697	0.882
Significance Value	0.006	0.004	0.001	0.017	0.023	0.128**	0.00	0.062**	0.007	0.210**	0.012	0.071

The results from Table 2 showcased the relationship between the responses of the predictor variable (Social media marketing platform as a trigger to actual purchase (see Table 2)and the likelihood of such reactions falling into one of the higher levels (strongly agree or agree) versus the lower level response (strongly disagree or disagree). In the actual purchase, statements are consistent across all six of the actual purchases statements in Nigeria.

Nigerian Generation Y' responses to 'Social network as a trigger to Actual purchase the likelihood of responding 'agreed' (compared to responding 'strongly agreed') to statements under 'Actual purchase' will increase by:

Almost 2 times over (1.958) for AP_NIG1.

More than 1 time over (1.797) for AP_NIG2.

More than 1 time over (1.452) for AP_NIG3.

More than 1 time over (1.568) for AP_NIG4.

More than 1 time over (1.350) for AP_NIG5.

More than 1 time over (1.531) for AP_NIG6.

Across their respective perceptions, Nigerian Generation Y believes that those factors contributing to 'Social network as a trigger to actual purchase (Table 2)' are related to those factors contributing to actual purchase. By implication, 'Social network as a trigger to actual purchase (Table 2)' statements showed that Nigerian Generation Y (amongst others) has effects on Actual Purchase statements in this study. Hence inference such as the following is drawn:

Generation Y in Nigeria agreed that social networks triggered them to engage in the actual purchase of brands/products' (that is, 2.7). More than 2 times over (over 200%) - brand loyalty. "there is the possibility that in future, my purchases of groceries and toiletries will be higher on social networking platform" (that is, AP_NIG1). Generation Y in Nigeria agreed that social networks triggered them to engage in actual purchase of brands/products', whilst for Nigeria, more than 1 time over (over 100%) good consumer service/ brand integrity. "I will buy via social media if the organisations possess good consumer service and high integrity" (that is, AP_NIG2).

Generation Y in Nigeria agreed that social networks triggered them to engage in actual purchase of brands/products' (that is, 2.7 see Figure 2). More than 1 time over (over 100%) Brand Awareness ("I will shop on social networking platform if I have knowledge or information about a brand" (that is, AP_NIG3) . Generation Y in Nigeria agreed that social network triggered them to engage in actual purchases of brands/products. In Nigeria, more than 1 times over (over 100%) Brand Fan-page "My engagement on brand Fan-page events will influence me to purchase via social media." (that is, AP_SA4 and NIG4).

Generation Y in Nigeria agreed that social networks triggered them to purchase brands/products. In Nigeria, more than 1 time over (over 100%) incentives "I will continue to purchase on social media as long as there are incentives for buying and participation" (that is, AP_NIG5). Generation Y in Nigeria agreed that social networks triggered them to engage in the actual purchase of brands/products' (that is, 2.7 see Table 2).

The Generation Y in Nigeria, more than one time over (over 100%) convenience and speed of transaction "buying on social networking sites gives me convenience and hastens my buying process" (that is, AP_NIG6). Thus, 'Social network as a trigger to actual purchase (2.7)' is a good predictor of statements under actual purchase in Nigeria among Generation Y to engage in actual purchase on social media platform under in this study.

6. Discussion of the findings

This research showed that the majority of Generation Y affirmed favourably to those factors that influence Generation Y to engage in actual purchase on social media platforms. The outcomes depicted that actual purchases on social media resulted influenced by the platform convenience and the active organisation participation in brand Fan-page events. Other solid reasons for social media marketing purchases can be factored in quickly and compare different brands with less cost (Kowalska, 2012). The ordinal logistic regression (OLR) results displayed the relationship between the responses of the predictor variable. It unfolds that 'social networking sites are regard as a trigger factor to actual purchase' (Table 2, statement 2.7). To begin

with, the result in this study revealed that there is a likelihood that in future, Generation Y' purchases of groceries and toiletries will be higher on social networking platforms.

This study supported Elms *et al.* (2016), which remarks that social media marketing offers an experience different from brick-and-mortar stores. The outcome has shown clearly that the social media marketing platform has a powerful and significant influence on consumers shopping methods and behaviour. These study findings affirmed by Josh and Vaghela's (2015) report that Generation Y consumer and social media marketing shopping information directly and favourable influences future online shopping intention. In line with the research objective, the findings showed how young consumer would continue to purchase on social networking platforms if they have prior information about a particular brand. The results agreed with the past study of Lupiáñez-Villanueva, Gaskell, Veltri, Folkvord, Bonatti, Bogliacino, Fernández, and Codagnone(2016). that social media platforms permit individuals to recommend to their loved ones and stranger who had experienced a particular product or brand.

As expected, a social network is significantly related to actual purchases. This study showed that Nigerian Generation Y believed that social networks triggered them to engage in the actual purchase of brands/products. They attest that buying on social networking sites gives them convenience and hastens their buying process. The results of this study findings align with the theory of technology acceptance model (TAM), underpinning this study. Furthermore, TAM (Davis, 1989) states that the application of novel skills hinges on individual behaviour towards the said skill. The nature of perceived ease and usefulness enhance the performance of these young cohorts on social media. This makes this Generation Y enthusiastic and keen to engage in their respective purchases via this new technology such as social media.

6.1. Contribution of the study

This study unknots important implications by contributing to social media marketing and marketing management; and showcased Generation Y attitude can on their respective favourable social platform. This study improves the understanding of the TAM model of Davis in 1989, which was incorporated into this study. This model deduced from this study that Generation Y perceived using a particular technology can improve their performance. This study also makes significant contributions to policymakers; there is a need to invest more resources into the information technology economy, since the achievements would spread to other sectors of the economy. In addition, the study noted that the nature of perceived ease and usefulness could enhance these young cohorts' participation on social media marketing platforms.

The empirical findings of this study provide a new understanding of potential threats, which might hinder the integration of marketing activities with social media users. Lastly, the findings recommended that social media play a significant role in the modern marketing communication industry. Lastly, this study will add more value to researchers, advertising agencies, public relations practitioners, and organisations in social media marketing and the business world at large.

7. Conclusion and recommendation

This study provides compelling evidence that social media is an emerging marketing tool in influencing Nigerian Generation Y to engage in actual purchases. Remarkably, young consumers will purchase social networking platforms if they have adequate information about a particular brand. Notably, social media marketing platforms are the primary influencers of Generation Y to engage in actual purchases. Gupta (2016) asserted that social network opinions are decisive factors influencing actual purchase behaviour among Generation Y. In a nutshell, information gathered via Generation Y actual purchase behaviour aids in designing an effective marketing strategy. Therefore, the findings of this study established the following recommendations:

- i. FMCGs brand manager should inspire Generation Y consumers to spend more time on social media marketing platforms via brand apps, online contests designed by the brands, and numerous shared marketing programmes designed to engage these young cohorts.
- ii. Advertisers should ensure that their respective brands are proactive on social media networks. It is essential for FMCGs brands must be active on social media platforms because there are numerous complaints, inquiries, comments, and customer service responsibilities to provide a solution for Generation Y consumers.
- iii. The organisation can partner with related social media brand influencers. Advertisers of FMCGs should partner their brand with trending influencers in the industry. Generation Y trust brand and product recommendations and reviews by influencers within their social circle. Thus, strangers do influence this young cohort on social media.

Finally, it recommended that further study be carried out because no single research can be all-inclusive, significantly biased towards social media marketing and Generation Y. Hence. There is a need for future research to establish other factors. This study focussed on fast-moving consumer goods (FMCGs) on social media marketing. It would be inspiring for future research to focus on the top-of-the-mind experience among the adults of other products such as manufacturing goods, services on social media marketing platforms.

8. Funding

The North-West University (NWU) Postgraduate Bursary supported this research paper.

ORCID

Enitan Olumide Olutade <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8683-3403>

References

1. Africa Practice. (2014). The social media landscape in Nigeria 2014: The who, the what, and the know Nigeria. *Africa Practice*. 1.
2. Africa Union. (2006). African Generation Y charter. Retrieved from https://www.un.org/en/africa/osaa/pdf/au/african_Generation_Y_charter_2006.pdf
3. Akintola, M & Bello, M. (2016). Usage of WhatsApp as a Social Media Platform among Undergraduates in Kwara State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Technology*, 3 (2):7-20.
4. Akintola, M., Bello, M.B., & Daramola, D.S. (2017). Usage of WhatsApp as a social media platform among undergraduates in Kwara State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Technology*, 2(1):67-80.
5. Akpan, C.S., Nwankpa, N.N., & Agu, V.O. (2015). Influence of Facebook advertisement on the buying behaviour of students of a Nigerian university. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 5(7):135-148.
6. Alsanie, S. I. (2015). Social media (Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp) used and its relationship with the university students contact with their families in Saudi Arabia. *Universal Journal of Psychology*, 3(3):69-72.
7. Arrigo, E. (2018). Social media marketing in luxury brands: a systematic literature review and implications for management research. *Management Research Review*, 41(6):657-679
8. Artemova, A. (2018). Engaging generation Z through social media marketing Case: Hurja Media Oy. (Thesis- Honour).
9. Bekoglu, F.B. & Onayli, C. (2016). Strategic approach in social media marketing and a study on successful Facebook cases. *European Scientific Journal*, 12(7):261-274.
10. Bevan-Dye, A. (2016). Profiling the generation y cohort. Inaugural Address at the Vaal Triangle Campus, North-West University. Vaal Triangle occasional papers: inaugural lecture Vanderbijlpark2016. Retrieved

from

<https://dspace.nwu.ac.za/bitstream/handle/10394/19706/Final%20ALBD%20PROFILING%20THE%20GENERATION%20Y%20COHORT%20%28Autosaved%29.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

11. Busalim, A.H., Hussin, A.R.C. & Iahad, N.A. (2019). Factors influencing customer engagement in social commerce websites: a systematic literature review. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 14(2):1-14.
12. Ciprian, P. (2015). The growing importance of social media in business marketing. *Quaestus Multidisciplinary Research Journal Quaestus*, (7):94-98.
13. Coulter, K.S. & Roggeveen, A. (2012). Like it or not Consumer responses to word-of-mouth communication in on-line social networks. *Management Research Review*, 35(9):878-899.
14. Creswell, J.W. (2014). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. 4th Edition. CA: Sage Publications.
15. Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P., & Warshaw, P. R. (1989). User acceptance of computer technology: A comparison of two theoretical models. *Management Science*, 35(8): 982–1003.
16. Duffett, R.G. (2017). Influence of social media marketing communications on Generation Y' attitudes, *Generation Y*, 18 (1):19-39.
17. Elms, J, De Kervenoael, R & Hallsworth, A. (2016). Internet or store. an ethnographic study of consumers' Internet and store-based grocery shopping practices. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 32 :234-243.
18. Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1977). Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior: an introduction to theory and research. *Philosophy and Rhetoric*, 10(2):130-132.
19. Futurum Research (2016). Marketing to millennials. Retrieved from https://futurumresearch.com/wp-content/uploads/woocommerce_uploads/2017/02/report_200117.pdf Accessed Aug. 23 2018.
20. Gupta, V. (2016). Impact of social media on purchase decision making of customers. *International Journal on Global Business Management & Research*, 5(2):73.
21. Hajli, M.N. (2014). A study of the impact of social media on consumers. *International Journal of Market Research*, 56(3):387-404.
22. Icha, O. & Edwin, A. (2016). Effectiveness of social media networks as a strategic tool for organisational marketing management. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 21(S2):1-19.
23. Ismail, S. & Mokhtar, S.S. (2016). Moderating role of perceived benefit on the relationship between attitude and actual purchase, *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(S7):22-28
24. Jiyoung, C. (2009). Shopping on social networking web sites: attitudes toward real versus virtual items. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 10, 1, pp. 77-93.
25. Josh, M.R. & Vaghela, M.P. (2015). Consumer innovativeness among college students towards movies in Surat City. *Tirpude's National Journal of Business Research*, 5(1).
26. Kaplan, A.M. & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59-68.
27. Kowalsk, M. (2012). The Internet impact on market behaviour of Generation Y. *Journal of International Studies*. 5(1):101-106.
28. KPMG. (2017). The truth about online consumers' 2017 global online consumer report. Retrieved from <https://assets.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/xx/pdf/2017/01/the-truth-about-online-consumerspdf> .
29. Krbová, P.K. (2016). Generation Y attitudes towards shopping: a comparison of the Czech Republic and Slovakia. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 64(2):626.
30. Lautiainen, T. (2015). Factors affecting consumers' buying decision in the selection of a coffee brand. Saimaa University of Applied Sciences, Lappeenrant (Thesis- Bachelor).
31. Maw, Y.A. (2016). Social media and best practice: the consumer brand relationship. (Doctoral Vega School of Brand Leadership (Thesis-Honours).

32. Mbanaso, U.M., Dandaura, E.S., Ezech, G.N. & Iwuchukwu, U.C. (2015). The use of social networking service among Nigerian Generation Y between ages 16 and 25 years in 2015. *International Conference on Cyberspace CYBER-Abuja* 14-21.
33. McKinsey & Company. (2019). Perspectives on retail and consumer goods. Retrieved from https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey/Industries/Retail/Our%20Insights/Perspectives%20on%20Retail%20and%20Consumer%20Goods%20Number%207/Perspectives-on-Retail-and-Consumer-Goods_Issue-7.ashx
34. Mefolere, K.F. (2016). WhatsApp and information sharing: prospect and challenges. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 4(1):615-625.
35. Mkwizu, K.H. (2019). Digital marketing and tourism: opportunities for Africa. *International Hospitality Review*.
36. Mulero, S.O. (2012). Acceptance and impact of social network marketing using extended technology acceptance model. Cape Peninsula University of Technology (Thesis-MTech).
37. Naumovska, L. (2017). Marketing communication strategies for Generation Y millennial. *Business Management and Strategy*, 8(1):123-133.
38. Olabanji, A. O., Shumba, P.M. & Tafadzwa, M. (2014). The impact of social media-based marketing on the turnover of retailers based in polokwane, South Africa, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science, MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy*.
39. Olotewo, J. (2016). Social media marketing in emerging markets. *International Journal of Online Marketing Research*, 2(2):10-18.
40. Olutade, E.O & Chukwere J.E. (2020). Greenwash as influencing factor to brand switching behavior among Generation Y in the social media age (In Naidoo V & Verma R, Marketing as a positive driver toward business sustainability, United States:. 219- 248).
41. Osazee-Odia, O.U. (2017). Investigating the influence of social media on sociability: A study of university students in Nigeria, *International Journal of International Relations, Media and Mass Communication Studies* 3(1):1-23.
42. Pew Research Center. (2014). Millennials in adulthood: Detached from institutions, networked with friends. Retrieved from <http://www.pewsocialtrends.org/2014/03/07/millennials-in-adulthood>
43. Rauniar, R., Rawski, G., Yang, J. & Johnson, B. (2014). Technology acceptance model (TAM) and social media usage: an empirical study on Facebook. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 27(1):6-30.
44. Rehman, F.U., Ilyas, M., Nawaz, T. & Hyder, S. (2014). How Facebook advertising affects buying behavior of Generation Y: the moderating role of gender. *Academic Research International*, 5(4):395-404.
45. Research Advisor (2006). Sample size calculator. Retrieved from <https://www.research-advisors.com/tools/SampleSize.htm>
46. Salwani, I.S., Marthandan, G., Norzaidi, M.D. & Chong, S.C., (2009). E-commerce usage and business performance in the Malaysian tourism sector: Empirical analysis, *Information Management and Computer Security*, 17(2):166-185.
47. Sanusi, R.B., Gambo, I.A. & Bashir, H. (2014). Use of social media among students of Nigerian polytechnic (In paper presented at international conference on communication, Media, technology and Design, Istanbul, Turkey) Retrieved from <http://www.cmdconf.net/2014/pdf/47.pdf>
48. Shivakumar, S.M. (2018). Social media marketing and its influence on millennials' buying behaviour. *BIMS International Research Journal of Management and Commerce*, 3(1).
49. Statista. (2017). Number of social media users worldwide from 2010 to 2020 (in billions). Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/278414/number-of-worldwide-social-network-users/>
50. Stephen, A.T. (2016). The role of digital and social media marketing in consumer behaviour. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 10:17-21.
51. Stueber, H., & Wurth, S. (2017). A Literature Review of Marketing and Facebook.

52. Su, C.C. & Chan, N.K. (2017). Predicting social capital on Facebook: the implications of use intensity, perceived content desirability, and Facebook-enabled communication practices. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 72:259-268.
53. Thaichon, P. (2017). Consumer socialization process: The role of age in children's online shopping behavior," *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Elsevier, 34(C):38-47.
54. Thurairaj, S., Hoon E.P., Roy, S.S. & Fong, P.K. (2015). Reflections of students. Language usage in social networking sites: making or marring academic English. *The Electronic Journal of e-Learning*, 13(4): 304-305.
55. Victor, V., Joy Thoppan, J., Jeyakumar Nathan, R. & Farkas Maria, F. (2018). Factors influencing consumer behavior and prospective purchase decisions in a dynamic pricing environment – An exploratory factor analysis approach. *Social Sciences*, 7(9):153.
56. Wang, X., Yu, C. & Wei Y. (2012). Social media peer communication and impacts on purchase intentions: a consumer socialization framework. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 26(4):198–208.
57. Yadav, M. & Rahman, Z. (2017). Social media marketing: Literature review and future research directions. *International Journal of Business Information Systems*, 25(2):213-240.
58. Zhang, T.C., Abound Omran, B. and Cobanoglu, C. (2017). Generation Y's positive and negative eWOM: use of social media and mobile technology. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29 (2) 732-761.

